

Notes

Stabilisation of Chromyl Ion by Some Potential Bidentate Ligands in Different Oxochloro Complexes of Quinquevalent Chromium

H. K. SAHA and S. K. GHOSH

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science,
Calcutta-700 009

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THE chemistry of quinquevalent chromium is dominated by chromyl ion, CrO^{3+} , which has so far yielded a few salts¹⁻⁵ of the species $[\text{CrOX}_4]^-$ and $[\text{CrOX}_5]^{2-}$ ($\text{X}=\text{F}$ or Cl). We have attempted to stabilise oxochromium(V) species, both in the ionic and non-ionic forms, using some potential bidentate (N-C-C-N type) ligands e.g., 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and 2-cyanopyridine (Cpy). Two salts of the species $[\text{CrOCl}_5]^{2-}$ and three non-electrolytic compounds, $[\text{CrOCl}_5 \cdot \text{L}]$ ($\text{L}=\text{bipy}$, phen or Cpy) have been synthesised and characterised by analytical data, determination of oxidation state and physicochemical investigations such as study of ir, esr and electronic spectra and measurements of magnetic susceptibility and conductance.

Experimental

All reagents used were of AR grade.

Chromium was estimated iodometrically after conversion to chromate by Na_2O_2 oxidation. Chlorine was estimated gravimetrically as silver chloride. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. Oxidation states were determined by iodometric method¹⁻⁵.

Preparation :

1. *2,2'-Bipyridylium oxopentachlorochromate(V)*, $\text{BipyH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$: CrO_3 (~1.0 g) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) by passing HCl gas. The base (1.0 g) dissolved in conc. HCl was added and passage of HCl gas was continued under ice-cold condition until bright red crystals separated out from the solution. The solution was filtered through gooch and the crystals dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~ 2.0 g. (Found : Cr, 12.76 ; Cl, 43.87 ; N, 6.85 Calcd. for $\text{BipyH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$; Cr, 12.95 ; Cl, 44.22 ; N, 6.97%). The oxidation state of chromium was found to be 5.02.

2. *1,10-Phenanthroline oxopentachlorochromate(V)*, $\text{PhenH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$: This was prepared following the same procedure as was used for the analogous bipyridylium salt, yield ~ 2.2 g. (Found : Cr, 12.13 ; Cl, 41.50 ; N, 6.49. Calcd. for $\text{PhenH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$; Cr, 12.22 ; Cl, 41.72 ; N, 6.66%). The oxidation state of chromium was found to be 5.05.

3. *Oxotrichloro(2,2'-bipyridyl)chromium(V)*, $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}]$: CrO_3 (~2.0 g) was dissolved in a mixture (30 ml) of glacial acetic acid and conc. HCl

(5 : 1 by volume) at room temperature and to the red solution thus obtained the base (1.0 g) was added in small portions with constant stirring after cooling the solution in ice-cold water. The red shining crystals obtained were separated by filtration and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, yield ~ 1.5 g. (Found : Cr, 15.42 ; Cl, 31.88 ; N, 8.42. Calcd. for $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}]$; Cr, 15.73 ; Cl, 32.25 ; N, 8.47%). The oxidation state of chromium was found to be 5.04.

4. *Oxotrichloro(1,10-phenanthroline)chromium(V)*, $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}]$: The procedure followed for the preparation of this compound was the same as that for the analogous bipyridyl compound, yield ~ 1.5 g. (Found : Cr, 14.26 ; Cl, 30.15 ; N, 7.69. Calcd. for $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}]$; Cr, 14.67 ; Cl, 30.04 ; N, 7.90%). The oxidation state of chromium was found to be 4.98.

5. *Oxotrichloro(2-cyanopyridine)chromium(V)*, $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Cpy}]$: A mixture of CrO_3 (1.5 g) and 2-cyanopyridine (2 ml) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was saturated with HCl gas and the red solution thus obtained was kept at ice-cold condition with occasional stirring until bright red crystals came out of the solution, yield ~ 1.0 g. (Found : Cr, 18.36 ; Cl, 37.95 ; N, 9.87. Calcd. for $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Cpy}]$; Cr, 18.67 ; Cl, 38.23 ; N, 10.06%). The oxidation state of chromium was found to be 5.01.

Results and Discussion

Conductance of the complexes was measured using dip type cell in acetonitrile and the molar conductance values obtained therefrom are given in Table 1. The conductance value of the salts $\text{LH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$ are in conformity with the values for 2 : 1 electrolytes in acetonitrile and those for the $[\text{CrOCl}_5 \cdot \text{L}]$ compounds are much less than the values for 1 : 1 electrolytes in the same solvent⁶. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using Gouy balance and the magnetic moments at room temperatures calculated, after diamagnetic corrections using Pascal's constant. The values are given in Table 1. The values for magnetic moments support the presence of chromium in d^1 configuration, as is also indicated by the values of oxidation states, but are slightly higher than those corresponding to the spin only values. This may be due to the effect of temperature independent paramagnetism. IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in KBr

TABLE I

Compound	$\nu(\text{Cr}=\text{O})$ cm^{-1}	Molar conductance mho cm^2	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\langle g \rangle$ values
$\text{BipyH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$	955	144.0	1.90 (297)	1.960
$\text{PhenH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$	950	124.14	1.97 (297)	1.976
$[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}]$	945	60.0	1.76 (301)	2.021
$[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}]$	945	54.0	1.86 (298)	2.034
$[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{py}]$	930	24.0	1.78 (302)	1.964

Values in parenthesis indicate the temperatures in degree absolute at which the magnetic susceptibilities were measured.

TABLE 2

Compound	Wavelength m μ	Bands kK	Molar extinction	Assignments
BipyH ₂ [CrOCl ₂]	720	13.89	100	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	590	16.94	190	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	460	21.74	580	³ B ₂ → ³ A ₁
				(xy → z ²)
	420	23.81	860	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	300	33.34	11500	π → π^*
PhenH ₂ [CrOCl ₂]	236	42.37	11800	(transition in bipyH ₂ ²⁺) ³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
	690	14.50	135	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	540	18.52	306	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	430	23.26	644	³ B ₂ → ³ A ₁
	335	29.85	7200	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	268	37.32	10120	π → π^*
				(transition in phenH ₂ ²⁺)
[CrOCl ₂ .bipy]	700	14.29	170	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	590	16.90	280	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	465	21.50	400	a ₂ (xy) → a ₁ (x ² -y ²)
	395	25.31	1050	a ₂ → a ₁ (z ²)
	278	35.97	16102	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]
	238	42.02	13900	π → π^*
				(in bipy)
[CrOCl ₂ .phen]	680	14.71	120	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	530	18.87	448	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	416	24.00	808	a ₂ → a ₁ [*]
	325	30.77	7360	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]
	246	40.46	12160	π → π^*
			(in phen)	
[CrOCl ₂ .Cpy]	750	13.33	50.0	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	600	16.69	148.80	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	450	22.22	421.40	b ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	395	25.31	562.0	a ₂ → a ₁ [*]
				(xy → x ² -y ²)
	310	32.25	5082	a ₂ → a ₁ [*] (z ²)
	250	40.00	8677	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]

phase in Perkin Elmer 621 spectrophotometer to locate different stretching bands, mainly Cr(V)=O stretching band. This band appears in all the compounds in the region 930-955 cm⁻¹ as has been observed previously in identical cases⁷⁻⁹. Electronic transition spectra both in the ultraviolet and visible regions were taken in Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer in acetonitrile and bands with probable assignments are given in Table 2. The assignments of bands are based on the work of McGlynn, Garner and Selbin on similar compounds^{9,10}. First derivative of esr absorption spectra of the powdered compounds were recorded in Alpha EPR spectrophotometer. The average <g> values were calculated (Table 1) which also support the paramagnetism corresponding to one unpaired electron.

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Molecular Adducts of Diphenyltin Diisothiocyanate with Some Nitrogen and Oxygen Donors*

(Mrs.) RAJESHWARI RUPAINWAR and B. D. PANDEY*
Chemistry Section, Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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THE synthesis and structural studies of diphenyltin dihalide complexes have been undertaken by certain research groups during the last fifteen years but only a few complexes of diphenyltin

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*Applied Chemistry Section, I.T., B.H.U., Varanasi.